

IMPACT OF FORCED LABOUR ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF UPPER PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS IN LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of forced labour on the academic performance of upper primary school pupils in Lagos State Nigeria. The study adopted a survey research design type. The population of the study comprised primary school pupils in Lagos State. The sample of the study consists "of" a total of two hundred and eighty-six (186) participants which are pupils in public primary schools. A multistage sampling technique was employed for the study. One research instrument was used for the study titled 'Force Labour on Academic Performance of Pupil (FLoAPoP). The instrument was validated by two experts in the Educational Foundations and Counselling Psychology department of the Lagos State University, Ojo Lagos. The reliability of the instrument was done through the use of the Cronbach Alpha technique and the coefficient value of $r = 0.74$. The findings reveal that there is a positive significant relationship between self-concept and academic performance of pupils in public primary schools. Also, there is a positive significant relationship between forced labour and the academic performance of primary school pupils. It was recommended that Children exposed to labour activities should be given equal rights to attend school regardless of any engagement in labour activity. Lastly, the child rights law should be fully implemented in Nigeria.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Forced Labour, School Attendance, Violence

Introduction

The issue of forced labour in Nigeria extends beyond mere statistics, revealing harrowing experiences faced by those subjected to such exploitation. Many individuals, especially young boys engaged in street vending, mining, and other labour-intensive sectors, endure gruelling conditions (Giammarinaro, 2018). They are often forced to work excessively long hours, exposing them to physical and emotional exhaustion. In the unregulated informal sector, children, particularly boys, are often found working in hazardous activities such as mining and stone quarrying, making them particularly vulnerable (Nwaubani, 2017). These dangerous working conditions can lead to significant health problems, with little to no concern for their welfare. Additionally, instances of sexual harassment and other forms of abuse are not uncommon, highlighting the harsh reality faced by those caught in forced labor (Dare, 2020). Similarly, young girls who should be attending primary school find themselves disproportionately affected, predominantly in domestic servitude (Reuters, 2020). Reports suggest that they are attracted to migration with promises of employment, education, or training, only to be exploited upon arrival. The abuse extends to physical and sexual violence, creating a pervasive atmosphere of fear and vulnerability (Eleweke, 2021).

The 2019 Human Rights Watch investigation shed light on the exploitation of Nigerian women and girls in traditionally 'female' sectors, such as domestic and care work (Malakooti, 2020). False promises of better opportunities lead them into situations where they endure exploitative conditions, including denial of basic needs like food and medical care (Spaggiari, 2020). In essence, the prevalence of forced labour in Nigeria is marked not only by the alarming number of reported cases but also by the deeply troubling experiences of those caught in its web (Oppenheim, M 2020). The National Agency for the Prohibition of Trafficking in Persons (NAPTIP) received reports of 52 and 27 cases of forced labour in Nigeria in 2020 and 2021,

respectively. Hence, an urgent need for comprehensive measures to address and eradicate this issue, as it reflects a dire violation of human rights and the dignity of the affected individuals.

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO) Forced Labour Convention, 1930 (No. 29), forced or compulsory labour encompasses all work or service extracted from an individual under the threat of penalty, without the person having offered themselves voluntarily. Forced labour is considered modern day slavery, where individuals are compelled to engage in work involuntarily, subjected to coercion through violence, intimidation, or subtler means such as manipulated debt, retention of identity papers, or threats of denunciation to immigration authorities (Siddharth, 2017). This stands in contrast to sub-standard or exploitative working conditions. Distinguishing forced labour from such conditions involves recognizing indicators like restrictions on freedom of movement, withholding of wages or identity documents, physical or sexual violence, threats, intimidation, or fraudulent debt that entraps workers (Benson-Idahosa et al.). Forced labour is not synonymous with sub-standard or exploitative working conditions. It is a distinct violation of fundamental human and labour rights and is legally considered a criminal offence (Umer, 2021).

Agbakwuru (2023) reported that the International Labour Organization (ILO) expressed concern about the worldwide occurrence of forced labour among underage children, stating that roughly 160 million children are currently involved in forced labour around the globe. This figure indicates a troubling rise of 8.4 million children compared to the 2021 report. In that report, it was disclosed that 50 million individuals were living in modern slavery, with 28 million of them subjected to forced labour. Regrettably, the incidence of modern slavery has witnessed a significant upsurge over the past five years, with 10 million more people falling victim to it in 2021 compared to the global estimates of 2016. The ILO, citing information from the Nigerian government, stated that approximately 15 million children are involved in forced labour in Nigeria. These affected children, aged between five and 17, are often employed in positions that rob them of their childhood, disrupt their education, or compromise their mental, physical, and social development (Adebayo, 2019). This is due to various factors, such as poverty, lack of qualitative education, unemployment, and lack of social security for vulnerable individuals, misinterpretation of cultural and religious beliefs, and a weak institutional framework (Seefar, 2021).

When young individuals engage in various forms of labour, they are prone to experience difficulty in maintaining focus, leading to a higher likelihood of eventually discontinuing their education (Pressly, 2021). This, in turn, hampers their academic performance and jeopardizes their prospects. Academic performance is a key measure of a pupil's success in school (Abidogun & Okechukwu, 2019). It is often employed to ascertain students' eligibility for admission to secondary schools, colleges, or universities, as well as their likelihood of graduating. The academic performance of students is of great significance and is a primary objective of education (Rono & Owino, 2014). It can be defined as the knowledge acquired by pupils, assessed through grades given by teachers, and aligned with educational objectives set by both pupils and teachers over a specific period (Narad & Abdullah, 2016).

Moreover, researchers have underscored the significant influence of pupils' regular attendance on their academic performance. School attendance, defined by Gottfried (2010), refers to learners' consistent participation in school-related activities. This continuous involvement in educational settings, as emphasized by Oghuvbu (2010), offers students the ongoing educational support necessary to improve their academic performance. Epstein and Sheldon (2002) further note that consistent school attendance demonstrates a commitment to classroom engagement from enrollment to the completion of a full academic program. However, children engaged in forced labour are automatically deprived of the opportunity to attend classes regularly, thereby impacting their academic progress.

Upper primary school pupils, typically spanning grades 4 to 6 and generally aged between 9 and 11 years, experience a transition to a more structured curriculum as they progress in their education. This curriculum places increased emphasis on critical thinking and a deeper understanding of subjects. As their cognitive development progresses, these children exhibit an increased ability to process information at a higher level and engage in analytical problem-solving, as observed by Binoya (2021). Conversely, the age range of upper primary school pupils aligns with the International Labour Organization's (ILO) report, which indicates that the children affected by forced labour in Nigeria fall between the ages of five and 17. Around 15 million children in Nigeria are affected by forced labour, often resulting in their employment in positions that rob them of their childhood, disrupt their education, and compromise their overall development (UNESCO, 2022)

Statement of the Problem

Despite significant progress in Nigeria's efforts to address forced labour, such as adopting and ratifying ILO Conventions 138 and 182, enacting the Child Rights Act in line with the Convention on the Rights of the Child, and reviewing and validating the National Policy on Child Labour and the Prohibition and Elimination of Forced Labour, this issue continues to worsen. This indicates that the initiatives to combat forced labour are ineffective despite policy interventions. According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), there are at least 15 million child workers in Nigeria, and the United Nations warns that without effective mitigation strategies, this number could exponentially increase, posing significant implications for the future. These affected children, aged between five and 17, are often employed in positions that rob them of their childhood, disrupt their education, or compromise their mental, physical, and social development (Adebayo, 2019). This is due to various factors, such as poverty, lack of education, unemployment, and lack of social security for vulnerable individuals, misinterpretation of cultural and religious beliefs, and a weak institutional framework. However, research has shown a limited correlation between forced labor and academic performance over time, prompting the need to explore the impact of forced labor on the academic performance of upper primary school students in Lagos State.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to examine the effect of forced labour on the academic performance of upper primary school pupils in Lagos State. Specifically, other objectives of this study are:

- ii. To determine if forced labour has an impact on the school attendance of the child.
- ii. To determine if forced labour has an impact on the academic performance of the child.
- iii. To examine ways in which forced labour can be curbed in Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be answered in this study:

H₁: There is no significant relationship between forced labour and school attendance of primary school pupils.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between forced labour and academic performance of primary school pupils.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design type. This design type helps to gather, organize and analyze data gotten from a pool of respondents and generalize its outcome on the larger population. The population for this study comprised all the primary school pupils in Lagos State. The choice of this local government area lies on the premise that public primary schools in

this area have been known to produce a mix of good and bad pupils after post-primary education. 186 pupils were the sample for this study. A Multistage sampling procedure was used for this study. A simple random sampling technique was used to select six local government educational authorities. A system sampling technique was used to select 31 pupils each from the six local government educational authorities. One research instrument was used for the study titled 'Force Labour on Academic Performance of Pupil (FLoAPoP). The instrument was validated by two experts in the Educational Foundations and Counselling Psychology department of the Lagos State University, Ojo Lagos. The reliability of the instrument was done using the Cronbach Alpha technique and the coefficient value of $r = 0.74$. Data collected were analyzed using inferential statistic of person product moment correlation PPMC at 0.05 of level of significance.

Results

H₁: There is no significant relationship between forced labour and school attendance of primary school pupil.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relationship between forced labour and school attendance of primary school pupils

Variables	N	Mean	Std.D	r	Sig	Remark
Forced Labour	186	26.72	16.52	3.75	0.000	significant
School Attendance	186	21.24	13.14			

Table above shows that there is a positive significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of pupils in public primary school ($r = 3.75$; $p < 0.05$). Therefore hypothesis one is rejected. The positive relationship implies that forced labour is considered as individuals are compelled to engage in work involuntarily, subjected to coercion through violence, intimidation, or subtler means such as manipulated debt, retention of identity papers, or threats of denunciation to immigration authorities (Siddharth, 2017). The extent to which pupils regularly attend school has a substantial impact on their academic performance; Gottfried (2010), sees school attendance are pertains to the consistent involvement of learners in school-related activities.

H₂: There is no significant relationship between forced labour and the academic performance of primary school pupils.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation showing the relationship between force labour and school attendance of primary school pupils

Variables	N	Mean	Std.D	r	Sig	Remark
Forced Labour	186	26.72	16.52	5.16	0.000	significant
Academic Performance	186	19.23	11.65			

Table 2 shows that there is a positive significant relationship between forced labour and the academic performance of primary school pupils ($r = 5.16$; $p < 0.05$). Therefore hypothesis two is rejected. The positive significant relationship implies that when young individuals engage in various forms of labour, they are prone to experience difficulty in maintaining focus, leading to a higher likelihood of eventually discontinuing their education (Pressly, 2021). Academic

performance is a key measure of a pupil's success in school (Abidogun & Okechukwu, 2019). It is often used to determine pupils' eligibility for admission to secondary schools, colleges, or universities and their chances of graduating. The academic performance of pupils holds immense importance and is a key goal of education (Rono, & Owino, 2014).

Conclusion

This study examined how forced labour affects the academic performance of upper primary school learners in Lagos State, Nigeria. This study has revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of pupils in public primary schools. The study revealed a noteworthy positive correlation, suggesting that when young people are involved in different types of work, they tend to struggle with maintaining concentration, thus increasing the probability of eventually dropping out of school.. Based on the result from the findings of this study, it was concluded that there was a significant effect of students' exposure to forced labour on the academic performance of upper primary school pupils in Lagos State. Also, there was a positive relationship implying that forced labour is considered as individuals are compelled to engage in work involuntarily, subjected to coercion through violence, intimidation, or subtler means such as manipulated debt, retention of identity papers, or threats of denunciation to immigration authorities.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were put forward:

1. Children involved in forced labour should have the same rights to access education as those who are not engaged in such activities.
2. The federal government of Nigeria should work towards the eradication of poverty by employing its citizens, which is the primary cause of forced labour.
3. The government and local communities need to devise constructive approaches to decrease forced labour demands, thereby ensuring children's consistent school attendance and academic success.
4. The full implementation and thorough monitoring of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programs are essential to safeguard children who are engaged in forced labour.
5. The child rights law should be fully implemented in Nigeria.

References

- Abidogun, B.G & Okechukwu, J, (2021). Impact of child labour on health and learning outcome of the child. *Eko. Journal of Educational Research volume 9*.
- Adebayo, B. (2019). 19 pregnant teens and women rescued from suspected baby traffickers in Nigeria, police say', *CNN*, 30 September. <https://edition.cnn.com//09/30/africa/nigeria-police-rescue-pregnant-women-from-traffickers/index.html>.
- Agbakwuru, J. (2023). Sustainable inland ports in Nigeria: an opportunity for growth of Nigerian nation. *Journal of Applied Sciences and Environmental Management*, 27(5), 965–973. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jasem.v27i5.12>
- Benson-Idahosa, E, Chun-turley, S, Ojewale, O, Olofin, R & Odo, N (2020). Pathway to Prevention: A Research Report on Recruiters of Sex Trafficking in Oredo LGA, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.
- Dare, A (2020). 'Beaten, raped and forced to work: why I'm exposing the scandal o Nigeria's house girls'<https://www.theguardian.com/lifeandstyle/2020/mar/17/beaten-raped-and-forced-to-work-why-im-exposing-the-scandal-of-nigerias-house-girls>.
- Eleweke, T (2021). 'Anambra Police rescue 4 pregnant girls in baby factory fronting as bar', *Daily Trust*, <https://dailytrust.com/anambra-police-uncover-baby-factory-with-4-pregnant-girls>.
- Epstein, J. L., and Sheldon, S. B. (2002). Present and accounted for: Improving student attendance through family and community involvement. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 95(5): 308-317.
- Giammarinaro, M. (2018). UN Special rapporteur on trafficking in persons, especially women and children', *Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights*.
- Gottfried, M. A. (2010). Evaluating the relationship between student attendance and achievement in urban elementary and middle schools: An instrumental variables approach. *American Educational Research Journal*, 47(2): 434-465.
- Human Rights Watch (2019). "You pray for death" *Trafficking of women and girls in Nigeria*. Available from: <https://www.hrw.org/repor/you-pray-death/trafficking-women-and-girls-Nigeria>.
- Malakooti, A. (2020). The intersection of irregular migration and trafficking in West Africa and the Sahel: Understanding the patterns of vulnerability, *Global Initiative against Transnational Organized Crime*, 71-79.
- NAPTIP, (2022). Turkish rights group raise alarm on trafficking of Nigerians to Northern Cyprus', <https://naptip.gov.ng/naptip-turkish-rights-group>.
- Narad, A., & Abdullah, B. (2016). Academic performance of senior secondary school students: influence of parental encouragement and school environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 8(2), 12–19. doi: 10.21659/rupkatha.v8n2.02
- Nwaubani, T. (2017). Trafficked, beaten, abuse; Life of a Nigerian house girl <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-nigeria-trafficking-children/trafficked->
- Oghuvbu, P. (2010). Attendance and academic performance of students in secondary schools: A correlational approach. *Studies on Home and Community Science*, 4(1): 21-25.
- Oppenheim, M. (2020), 'They are held against their will': Women rescued from 'baby-making' factory in Nigeria'<https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/africa/baby-making-factory-Nigeria-ogun>.
- Pressly, L. (2021). 'Trafficked to Europe for sex: A survivor's escape story' <https://www.bbc.com/news/stories>.
- Reuters Staff (2020). 'Nigerian police free children, pregnant teens from 'baby factory'', *Reuters*, 28 February. <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-nigeria-captives-babies/nigerian-police-free-children-pregnant-teens-from-baby-factory>.
- Seefar (2021). The Impact of COVID-19 on migration intentions and human trafficking in Benin

- city, Nigeria, 1-27. <https://seefar.org/wp-content/uploads>.
- Siddharth, K (2017). *Modern Slavery: A global perspective*, Columbia University Press, pp. 54-55.
- United Nations General Assembly (2019). Visit to Nigeria: Report of special rapporteur on trafficking in persons, <https://www.ohchr.org/en/documents/country-reports/ahrc4146add1-visit-nigeria-report-special-rapporteur-trafficking-persons>.
- United Nations Security Council (2020). Children and armed conflict in Nigeria: *Report of the Secretary-General S/2020/652*, 2-13. <https://documents-dds>